

Virtualized Infrastructure Managers for edge computing: OpenVIM and OpenStack comparison

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Abstract—The evolution of the centralized cloud computing architecture towards the edge of the network, driven by virtualization technologies such as Software-Defined Networking (SDN), Network Functions Virtualization (NFV) and Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC), brings new opportunities to the multimedia industry. Offloading computing power to the edge, local caching, minimized latency and flexibility in the deployment of services are only some of the benefits that the multimedia can gain from utilizing the edge computing capabilities. To achieve such progress the potential elements of an edge computing framework have to be studied and evaluated. In this work we focus on the component managing the edge resources which is defined as the Virtual Infrastructure Manager (VIM) in the MEC reference architecture. We analyze the time overhead which virtual machines (VMs) provisioning brings into the system. This is done by a comparison of the performance of two popular open-source solutions, OpenStack and OpenVIM, through extending an open-source benchmarking framework called CloudBench.

Index Terms—Virtual Infrastructure Manager, OpenStack, OpenVIM, Edge Computing, CloudBench, Open Source, Benchmark, Performance

I. INTRODUCTION

The recent convergence of key virtualization technologies such as Software-Defined Networking (SDN), Network Functions Virtualization (NFV), Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) and Fifth Generation (5G) wireless systems, has pushed the traditional centralized cloud computing architectures to the edge of the network, in close proximity to the end devices. Multimedia applications are amongst the most beneficial from the cloud evolution which brings minimized latency, offloading network traffic and computing power, local caching, flexibility and added security. However, the edge computing paradigm will stay on only if it meets the newly opened challenges including scalability, usage of heterogeneous resource-constrained devices, limited network throughput etc [1].

The first step towards a successful application of edge computing principles is the evaluation of the different components involved in one such framework. In this work we focus on the management of an edge computing infrastructure which is performed by Virtualized Infrastructure Managers (VIMs) as defined by the European Telecommunications Standards Institute (ETSI). In particular we analyze the time overhead which virtual machines (VMs) provisioning brings into the system. We do a comparison of two widespread open-source solutions - OpenStack [2] and OpenVIM [3] by extending

and utilizing the capabilities of an open-source benchmarking framework called CloudBench [4].

The rest of the paper is structured as follows. Section II presents related work and state-of-the-art in open-source cloud benchmarking tools. In Section III, we compare the logical architecture of OpenStack and OpenVIM while the experiment setup and results are described in Section IV. We conclude our research and outline future efforts in Section V .

II. RELATED WORK

ETSI has put efforts into standardizing the edge computing components by founding the Multi-access Edge Computing (MEC) group [5] which specifies an edge platform built on an NFV infrastructure that should leverage the NFV management and orchestration (MANO) [6] architecture and application programming interfaces (APIs).

Several works like [7] and [8] study the overall challenges in a MANO framework while presenting existing projects and products.

A recent research on the problems of operating edge computing infrastructures [9] is concentrated only on OpenStack. Another study [10] is measuring the performance and VM instantiation times of OpenStack and Nomad [11] and adds a reference model of the VNF instantiation process. The authors focus on tuning the performance of the two VIMs rather on their direct comparison.

Existing comparisons of cloud managers give us possible criteria for their evaluation. A work from [12] provides results of OpenStack and CloudStack benchmarking [13] and defines scenarios for VM creation/deletion times measurements. A comparison between OpenStack and Eucalyptus [14] done by [15] gives virtualization management metrics as well as results from industry standard tests.

Provisioning latency and provisioning throughput are the most relevant metrics for VIMs evaluation [4]. Based on them parameters like scalability, stability and reliability of the cloud computing platform can be identified.

Open-source tools for clouds benchmarking already exist and gain popularity. PerfKitBenchmark [16] gives simple and unified commands and tools to measure end to end resource provisioning time and peak performance metrics of the supported cloud providers. Rally [17] is a generic testing tool dedicated to OpenStack deployment and verification. Cloud

Rapid Experimentation and Analysis Tool (CloudBench) provides a cloud benchmarking framework collecting runtime performance as well as cloud management metrics.

We focus on the evaluation of one particular component from the ETSI MANO architecture - the VIM and in particular the open-source implementations which can be directly mapped to it - OpenStack and OpenVIM. OpenStack, although not formally adopted by ETSI, is the most common choice for the role of a VIM, while OpenVIM is part of ETSI Open Source MANO (ETSI OSM), the practical implementation of an ETSI MANO stack. Having the goal of benchmarking the VIMs as platforms and not the performance of the VMs running in the cloud, we will test the platforms provisioning latency by using CloudBench. Such direct comparison is missing in the literature up to now and can serve as a reference for future VIMs estimations and benchmarking.

III. VIM ARCHITECTURES COMPARISON

A. OpenStack logical architecture

OpenStack is developed as an open-source project with the goal of being a cloud operating system managing large-scale compute, storage and networking resources. Its logical architecture is composed of modules, developed as separate projects.

Fig. 1: OpenStack logical architecture

The OpenStack documentation prescribes the installation of the following services for minimal deployment (Figure 1):

- *Compute* creates and terminates virtual machines' (VMs) instances, tracks the inventory and usage, takes requests from the message queue and determines on which host to run VMs.
- *Networking* gives full control over creation of virtual network resources to tenants in the form of tunneling protocols.
- *Image* provides users with the capability to upload and discover VM images and metadata definitions.
- *Identity* has the main purpose of authorization and authentication of users

The addition of *Dashboard* and *Block Storage* is pointed as advisable.

The services interact with each other through public APIs and Advanced Message Queuing Protocol (AMQP). Users gain access through dashboard and command-line interfaces (CLIs).

B. OpenVIM logical architecture

OpenVIM is a lightweight VIM which follows the NFV principles with interfaces to the compute domain of the NFV Infrastructure and relying on OpenFlow controller (OFC) [18] for the network infrastructure.

The logical architecture of OpenVIM is simple, consisting of only one service, driving the main functionality. It is complemented by a CLI tool, RESTful API and a MySQL database. The "normal" operation mode implies the deployment of a controller with one or more compute nodes and requires integration with an OFC for managing the networking between them. A "host only" mode where the installation can be done on only one host without the need of an OFC is also available.

Fig. 2: OpenVIM logical architecture

The OpenVIM service (openvimd) is the core component of the architecture and is responsible for the creation, deletion and inventory of VMs, networks and images. Each functionality of the service is executed in a separate thread (DB management, HTTP server, Network controllers). OpenVIM relies on libvirt and Kernel-based Virtual Machine (KVM) running on the hosts to provide the virtualization infrastructure. A single thread is dedicated for each host (compute node) and Secure Shell (SSH) is used for the communication between the OpenVIM service and libvirt as shown on Figure 2. Two types of network management are supported: "bridge" and "ovs". Pre-provided network bridges with Layer 2 (L2) connectivity and an external Dynamic Host Configuration Protocol (DHCP) server are needed for the former. In case of the latter, Open vSwitch (OVS) Virtual Extensible LAN (VXLAN) tunnels are created.

A CLI tool called *openvim* is provided, running on the same or on a separate machine.

C. VIMs at the edge

Necessary properties of software running at the edge is to be efficient, scalable and distributable. OpenStack architecture is meant to be flexible and expandable and allows additional services to be added. The communication between modules is done through messaging which brings overhead to the systems but allows horizontal scaling. OpenVIM is created with the intention to provide the minimal functionalities of a VIM and consists of a single service spawning multiple threads. This leads to more efficient implementation but with less possibilities for extension. It lacks many of the complementary services of OpenStack - Dashboard, Identity, Telemetry etc. Both VIMs can be scaled horizontally by adding additional compute nodes although they lack inherent capabilities for automatic node discovery. The modularity of OpenStack makes the multiplication of the controller node possible with some additional efforts, while OpenVIM does not foresee controller scaling.

Both projects are implemented entirely in Python, which makes them rather independent from the underlying architecture. However, additional investigation should be done to take into account the heterogeneous resource-constrained devices common for the network edge. OpenStack is capable of running on ARMv8, despite some known issues related to the interaction with the hypervisor and the configuration of devices. OpenVIM has been officially tested only on Xeon E5-based Intel processors and the behavior on other architectures is not described.

IV. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP AND RESULTS

None of the existing cloud benchmarking tools support both OpenStack and OpenVIM. With the goal of reusing a test platform supporting multiple cloud adapters and having the possibility to compare them, we have extended the CloudBench (CB) framework by implementing a new cloud adapter for OpenVIM. CloudBench already supports OpenStack (Figure 3).

Fig. 3: CloudBench architecture [19]

The automated steps performed by CB while conducting the measurements are shown in Figure 4. Step 1 is performed only in the case when VMs are deployed implicitly by a submitter

TABLE I: OpenStack and OpenVIM flavors description

Name	RAM, MB	Disk, GB	VCPUs
tiny	1024	1	1
small	2048	20	1
medium	4096	40	2
large	8192	80	4

daemon and is not relevant to our experiments. The steps 5-10 follow the guest operating system (OS) boot which is highly dependent on the type of OS chosen and the applications running on it. Considering these reasons we focus only on steps 2-4 and define the following metrics:

- *VM provisioning request sent* (step 2) - the time overhead added by the VIM while collecting pre-provisioning data for images, flavors and existing VMs.
- *VM provisioning request completed* (steps 3 and 4) - the time elapsed between submitting the VM provisioning request and the VM status changed to "running". It is further split in two stages: request submission (step 3) and VM instantiation (step 4).
- *VM deprovisioning request completed* - the time elapsed between submitting the VM deprovisioning request and the actual VM removal. The steps for submitting a deprovisioning request are exactly the same as for provisioning and are not depicted on the figure.

In addition we measure the times to get a response for basic requests from the VIMs - get images, flavors, check existing instance.

OpenStack and OpenVIM use flavors to define the compute, memory, and storage capacity of the VMs, hence we conducted a series of experiments with varying flavors looking for a correlation with the VM creation times. Flavors, common for both VIMs, are described in Table I.

A. Extending CloudBench framework

The CloudBench framework is written in Python with extensibility and flexibility in mind and has a layered architecture shown in Figure 3. The support for OpenVIM was incrementally added by implementing a new cloud adapter without major changes in the main source code. To achieve this a prior research on OpenVIM mechanisms was needed to understand how to: connect to the cloud, list images flavors and SSH keys, list and get relevant information about instances. In summary, the changes are one new configuration file and one new Python class implementation, consisting of 800 lines of code.

The performed steps for adding a new cloud adapter can be described as:

- Implemented a new class `OvimCmds` in `cbtool/lib/clouds/ovim_cloud_ops.py`, in which CloudBench abstract operations are mapped to five mandatory methods: `vmccleanup`, `vmregister`, `vmunregister`, `vmcreate`, `vmdestory`. Other complementary methods are mandatory for implementation: `test_vmc_connection`, `is_vm_running`, `is_vm_ready`.

Fig. 4: CloudBench VM deployment steps [20] with steps relevant to the experiment zoomed in top-right.

TABLE II: Minimum requirements comparison

	OpenVIM	OpenStack Controller node	OpenStack Compute node
Processors	1	1	1
Memory	2 GB	4 GB	2 GB
Storage	40 GB	5 GB	10 GB
OS	Ubuntu Server 64-bit	Linux 64-bit	Linux 64-bit

- Created a new configuration template file with OpenVIM-specific parameters: `cbtool/configs/templates/_openvim.txt`
- Extended the existing configuration file `cbtool/configs/cloud_definitions.txt` to include the following user-defined OpenVIM parameters:

```
[USER-DEFINED : CLOUDOPTION_MYOPENVIM]
OVIM_ACCESS = http://localhost:9080/openvim
OVIM_TENANT = tenant_uuid
OVIM_NETNAME = mgmt
OVIM_LOGIN = cbuser
```

B. Test environment

A comparison of the minimum requirements for the deployment of a proof-of-concept environment for the two managers is shown in Table II. OpenStack is deployment through Devstack [21] and OpenVIM is configured to work in "host only" mode. For a hypervisor we use KVM (Kernel-based Virtual Machine), an open-source software with kernel component included in the mainline Linux [22]. In order to have an equal test environment the VIMs were deployed on a single host with the following configuration: Intel(R) Xeon(R) CPU E5-2623 v4 @ 2.60GHz with 32GB memory and 4TB storage and Ubuntu 16.04.1 Server operating system with KVM-enabled 4.4.0-31-generic Linux kernel.

C. Benchmarking results

All metric were collected by repeating each experiment for the four different flavors described in Table I. The VMs were

created one by one and deleted immediately afterwards so that the system load did not affect the VIMs performance. The gathered numbers are the result of repeating 20 identical test iterations and calculating the mean and standard deviation.

The comparison of VM provisioning request sent/completed and VM deprovisioning are shown on Figures 5, 6 and 7. OpenVIM shows better performance than OpenStack in all three tests. There is a small variation of OpenStack provisioning request completed times with respect to the flavor which can be attributed to the scale. While with OpenVIM there is a visible correlation between the flavor size and the provisioning times. There is no correlation between deprovisioning times and flavor in none of the VIMs results.

Figure 8 shows the split of the provisioning time. The most time consuming stage for both VIMs is the VM instantiation time. Figure 9 gives a comparison of VIM response times when requested for image, flavor and existing VMs information where OpenVIM achieves much smaller times. These results give a base for further analysis of the internal mechanisms and bottlenecks inside a VIMs architecture.

Fig. 5: "VM provisioning request sent", average time with standard deviation

Fig. 6: "VM provisioning request completed" average time with standard deviation

Fig. 9: VIM basic response, average time with standard deviation

Fig. 7: "VM deprovisioning request completed" average time with standard deviation

Fig. 8: VM provisioning request stages

V. CONCLUSION

This paper examined the logical architecture of two open-source solutions, OpenStack and OpenVIM, matching the functionalities of an ETSI VIM. We discussed their application in the context of edge computing and evaluated their performance by comparing the time for provisioning and deprovisioning VMs. We also implemented a new cloud adapter for OpenVIM in the existing cloud benchmarking framework CloudBench, in order to have a tool for fair comparison between cloud managers.

OpenVIM shows better performance than OpenStack in all test cases and this gives it an advantage in a resource-constrained environment such as the edge. However it lacks

support and development activities from the community. Part of its high performance comes at the expense of missing functionalities and authentication and security features. On the other side, although being more complex and general-purpose, OpenStack is massively adopted and updated regularly. Its flexibility allows for the creation of custom solutions for the needs of the edge and makes it the preferable choice of the authors.

The results of this work can be a foundation for further analysis and identifications of weak components in both solutions as well as comparison with other available products in the area.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 761508 (H2020 5GCity project).

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